

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	D2.1
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	2023-06-30	Version	1.0

Deliverable 2.1

Plan for exploitation, dissemination and communication

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Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	2023-06-30	Version	1.0

Document History:

Release	Date	Reason for Change	Status	Distribution
1.0		Initial document, reviewed	Released	External

To cite this document

Heard J, Derval C, Giunta V, Melet A, Steenbeek, J, Romero, L and Ciavatta S. (2023). D2.1 Plan for exploitation, dissemination and communication. Deliverable report of project Horizon Europe NECCTON (grant 101081273), Doi [10.5281/zenodo.8099626](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099626)

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Glossary

ARC: Arctic Ocean

BAL: Baltic Sea

BGC Argo: Biogeochemical Argo

BS: Black Sea

CI: Conservation International

CNECT OSPAR: Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic

CUAG: Champion User Advisory Group

DA: data assimilation

EOOS: European Ocean Observing System

ESA: European Space Agency

EU DG CNECT: Directorate-General for Communications Networks

EU DG MARE: Maritime Affairs and Fisheries - European Commission

EU DG: European Directorate-general

EUMETSAT: European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites

EMODnet: European Marine Observation and Data Network

EuroGOOS: European component of the Global Ocean Observing System

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation

GEO: Group on Earth Observations

GEOSS: Global Earth Observation System of Systems

GLO: Global Ocean

GOOS: Global Ocean Observing System

HTL: Higher Trophic Level

IBI: Iberia-Biscay-Ireland Region

ICES: International Council for the Exploration of the Sea

IMAR: Institute of Marine Research, Portugal, and DRAM: Regional Directorate for Maritime Affairs

ISSF: International Seafood Sustainability Foundation

IUCN: International Union for Conservation of Nature

LTL: Lower Trophic Level

MED: Mediterranean Sea

MFCs: Monitoring and Forecasting Centres

NWS: North-West European Shelf

OceanViz: interactive underwater visualization

PEDCR: Plan for exploitation, dissemination, and communication

SPC: Pacific Community

STAC: Scientific and Technical Advisory Committee

TACs: Thematic Data Assembly Centres

UN SDG: United Nations Sustainable Development Goals

UNEP: UN Environment Programme

UN-FAO: Food and Agriculture Organization, United Nations

UN-IOC: International Oceanographic Commission of United Nations

WP: work package

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1. Publishable summary

NECCTON aims at transforming the European capability to predict and protect the biodiversity of marine ecosystems. New modelling products of fisheries, pollution and benthic habitats will enable the Copernicus Marine Service to better inform ocean policy makers, managers and the public.

Through implementation of an effective communication and dissemination strategy the work-package 2 (WP2) of NECCTON, in collaboration with all the partners and WPs, will create a strong brand identity for NECCTON that will appeal and engage potential users of NECCTON new products.

2. Objectives

Communication objectives

The overall objective of NECCTON is to enable Copernicus Marine Service to deliver products that inform the conservation of marine biodiversity and the sustainable management of food resources, by fusing innovative ocean ecosystem models and new data. In order to achieve this objective the NECCTON Communication and Dissemination Team (PML, MOi, Eii and Lobelia in WP2) will produce materials that promote the project and its achievements as well as targeted exchanges with specially identified stakeholders, including those implementing the Copernicus Marine Service core services.

Communication measures will initially focus on the dissemination of NECCTON objectives and co-design activities. As the project matures communication activities and tools will focus on sharing its achievements and engaging users of the products.

Dissemination and exploitation objectives

A core aim of WP2 is to generate impact from the project by targeting specific groups such as Copernicus Marine Service core services and users, academic communities and policy makers using scientific language and utilising channels including scientific journals and conferences, research networks, and online repositories of data to maximise the uptake of the results from the project. This differs from the communication objectives which aims to create more general awareness and enhance the visibility of the project using non-specialised language utilising channels such as websites, newsletters, social and traditional media.

The long-term exploitation strategy of NECCTON consists in the potential integration of the new products in Copernicus Marine Service, prioritising user and policy needs. Mercator Ocean has been designated an entrusted entity by the European Commission to implement the Copernicus Marine Service, and will ensure the alignment of NECCTON to the overall Copernicus Marine Service evolution needs, strategy and plans and the transferability of NECCTON to that Service. Other partners are core developers of Copernicus Marine Service Monitoring Forecasting Centres, MFCs (PML, OGS, UKMO, UoL, BSH, NERSC) and Copernicus Marine Service Thematic Assembly Centres, TACs (CNR), ensuring the technical alignment between NECCTON and Copernicus Marine Service systems. All the core developer partners, as well as the Mercator Ocean International, engage on a regular basis with data providers (e.g., ESA, EUMETSAT and national space agencies like the Italian Space Agency) to define data needs, channels of data flow, provide feedback on data quality and exploitability. Appropriate stakeholders, for example, those already engaged in the project as case-studies co-designers, will be

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engaged to explore these new products by exploiting an innovative and specific visualization tool linked with from the Copernicus Marine Service MyOcean viewer. The mid-to-long term exploitation of NECCTON will be through an integration of NECCTON’s legacy products and services in Copernicus Marine Service and will be presented in the key deliverable **D2.3 Strategic roadmap for the uptake of NECCTON by Copernicus Marine Service** ([section 5.4](#)).

3. Introduction

Through effective communication and dissemination WP2 aims to create a strong, attractive brand identity for NECCTON that will appeal to potential users of the NECCTON next generation of products. WP2 will communicate internally and externally with the Copernicus Marine Service, stakeholders, potential end-users and the general public about the progress of the project and key achievements and to create NECCTON brand awareness. Through clear and targeted communications the work package aims to attract and motivate potential end users to maximize the impact of NECCTON activities and outputs.

The main objectives of the exploitation, dissemination and communication activities are:

1. Ensure effective and productive communication **within the project** (WP1 and 2) through the establishment and maintenance of a defined participant network, so that the communication of results, events, news, products and services can be targeted as required.
2. **External promotion** of NECCTON objectives and its aims to raise awareness and generate interest in its products as these become available, as well as fostering an on-going relationship with the Copernicus Marine Service core services and other relevant stakeholders encouraging multidirectional communication and developing contact networks.
3. **Identification of contacts within the stakeholder groups and end users** to develop a contacts database (subject to GDPR) to support tailored messaging aligning with Plan for exploitation, dissemination and communication activities. A group of key stakeholders was set up at the start of the project, and is involved with the case study managers in monitoring product developments. This list will expand as networks and contacts grow throughout the project.
4. **Communicate** the project’s outputs and outcomes to the stakeholders, participant network and beyond, through the use of products such as the project website, social media, visualizations and targeted training events. The dedicated project website has been made by PML, which will be regularly updated (<https://www.neccton.eu/>).
5. **Co-design** through workshops and training events, starting at the beginning of the project (first stakeholder co-design workshop, June 2023), and thereafter regular meetings with the key-stakeholders already engaged in the project and case-studies leaders during the first phase of the project to ensure products are aligned with user’s needs.

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6. **Promote the products and demonstrators** through on-line training sessions, focused towards the end of the project. This will support **capacity building** by transferring knowledge from project partners to the end-users and vice versa.

Communication tools (website, newsletters, visualisations, conference presentations, social media etc) will be updated regularly during the project and will be adapted as needed to target particular audiences and prioritize key messages.

3.1 Scope of document

Clear and effective communication on the progress and innovation of NECCTON are vital to the success of the project. The ability to raise awareness, engage interest and develop the user community of NECCTON's new and enhanced products within the Copernicus Marine service and their stakeholders is crucial. This will affect the outcome of the project and the success of the products to evaluate biodiversity and food resources in support of policy implementation and user requirements.

This document sets out the objectives and plan for communication and dissemination activities as defined at the start of the project. It will serve as a guide to ensure consistent and focused communication for project participants to ensure clear and coherent presentation of the NECCTON vision and approach to its broad stakeholder audience. The plan for Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication (PEDCR) as described in this document outlines the communication methodology, target audience, communication goals and objectives, key messages, major lines of communication and key performance indicators that we will use to evaluate the impact of the communication actions.

3.2 Intended audience

This document is primarily designed as a guide for NECCTON participants. All NECCTON partners will be involved in communication and dissemination activities, so it is vital to have a logical and coherent structure to our activities. WP2 will work closely with WP1 (Management) and WP9 (Case studies) to ensure that communications are targeted and pitched appropriately to each audience.

3.3 Evolution of document

The PEDCR is intended to be a living document and will be reviewed periodically to ensure it meets the needs of the project as it develops. A major revision will be undertaken by month 24 at the halfway mark of the project to ensure we are hitting targets and connecting with the right audiences.

4. Dissemination and communication strategy management

Mercator Ocean leads WP2 'Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication' with input from PML and all NECCTON partners. To support the efficient coordination and management of dissemination and communication activities the follow measures are in place:

- An online dissemination register to collect details of NECCTON partners attendance at events – details of activities will be reported through the periodic reporting mechanism.

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- Maintenance of an editable register/contacts audience database of NECCTON stakeholder and end-users in compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679. Interested audiences can sign up directly through the dedicated project website (<https://www.neccton.eu>) to this register. The register will be continuously updated throughout the life of the project.
- Management of individual tasks/activities/deliverables with reminders for deadlines through the project management portal.
- Quarterly project meetings with WP leads to ensure smooth coordination of joint activities.
- Working Groups on specific topics, including visualization and management of the NECCTON products.

Ongoing and completed dissemination and communication activities will be reported in Progress Reports (WP1) and compiled into a document that will form part of the Final Report.

Figure 1 highlights WP2’s role in the achieving overall project impact and interaction with other WPs across the project.

Figure 1 Schematic of the key elements of NECCTON's impact pathway

4.1 Distribution of key responsibilities

All partners will contribute to communication, dissemination and exploitation of results. However the main task of WP2 are led by several partners as listed below:

T2.1 Stakeholders: engagement and co-development (MOi). A demonstration-aided, co-design workshops was held in June 2023, to better inform the product specifications in other WPs including WP9 case studies. Additional workshops with the use case leaders and associated stakeholders will take place during the first 2 years of the project.

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T2.2 Visualization (Lobelia; EII). A serverless lightweight datacube viewer will be implemented for NECCTON using Lobelia Explore, for the visualization, analysis and dissemination of the NECCTON datasets in compliance with the most advanced dissemination protocols of Copernicus Marine Service data (see the details in the deliverable D1.1 “Initial Data Management Plan (DMP))

T2.3 External communication (PML). Coordinate internal and external communication activities. Develop NECCTON brand and increase awareness and understanding of the NECCTON products in the potential user community.

T2.4 Dissemination (PML, plus all partners). Dissemination of project results and key events and through peer reviewed publications.

T2.5 Long-term exploitation / integration in Copernicus Marine (MOi). Ensure the legacy and long-term exploitation of the project via the integration of NECCTON new products and services in the Copernicus Marine Service.

4.2 Policies and rules

As indicated in section 5.2.3 **General communication factors** communication activities will follow appropriate cultural and gender guidelines to ensure all products appeal to a wide audience and do not discriminate. All data stored will be compliant with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR; Regulation (EU) 2016/679).

5. Dissemination and communication plan

This section sets out the dissemination and communication plan for NECCTON in detail including outlining the tools that will be utilised and the key tasks and milestones.

Effective communication and dissemination of the NECCTON progress and ultimate products are essential to the success of the project. WP2 will ensure that well-tailored and directed marketing messages are delivered through a range of communication channels in order to create awareness and invite more users to participate in the co-design process. A series of capacity building events, targeted at the users, will be organised to increase uptake and adoption of NECCTON products.

The main strategic communication objective of NECCTON is to ensure that the projects’ activities, progress and key achievements are translated into a meaningful call to action, clearly demonstrating the benefits of the new and innovative model products produce for use by Copernicus Marine Service communities. The communication activities will focus on:

1. Building the NECCTON brand and demonstrating the potential of NECCTON and, therefore, increasing the level of engagement in the project;
2. Creating general awareness of the capability of NECCTON products and tools to enhance food security by informing the sustainable management of fisheries.
3. Increasing public awareness with respect to the importance of monitoring and preserving marine biodiversity to improve public support for such activities, through information shared on the project website and social media through infographics and simple visualisations.

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4. Using innovative visualization tools and products to clearly communicate NECCTON results and engage audiences.
5. Engaging stakeholder audiences through a series of co-design workshops, surveys and training events.

While materials will be primarily in English, local language communications will draw on the facilities of the rest of the consortium. All the communication materials will include the European Commission logo, grant number and EC funding acknowledgement.

NECCTON will employ a range of communication channels, designed to suit the needs of the project participants, end-users and other stakeholders. To facilitate this a contacts database will be established early in the project enabling targeted communication with interested parties.

The NECCTON website (www.neccton.eu) was developed during the setup phase to provide a globally accessible focal point for NECCTON communication activities. Social media feeds have been embedded into the site to enable users to easily view and comment upon the latest news from the project. The website will act as a 'shop-front' and repository providing details on projects objectives, outputs and products, technical information, links to freely downloadable data sets, visualisation platform and videos, science contacts and highlights of the research. It will support the visibility of the project for other end users and the wider scientific community.

5.1 Subject of dissemination

Dissemination is the act of gaining the attention of stakeholders and making the results of research available to them in a form that they can comprehend and use. In the context of NECCTON this will mean increasing the visibility of the project to potential end users and other stakeholders. By actively engaging users in a two-way dialogue, through internal meeting with our key-stakeholders and workshops with a wider community of potential users, such as end-users reached through the Copernicus Marine Service, and the Champion user groups from WEkEO and Copernicus Marine, we will be able to deliver the information they need in a format that is useful to them. This will ensure optimum uptake of NECCTON products and the maximum benefit derived from their implementation.

5.2 Dissemination strategy

This section sets out the target audience for dissemination activities, and the tools activities and events that will be used to reach them. Each stakeholder will have different needs and interests so a wide range of tools and activities are planned.

5.2.1 Target audience

NECCTON intends to reach the largest number of relevant stakeholders at a local, national, regional and global level in order to support key decision makers with the benefits and value of integrating and improved products into the Copernicus Marine Service to better inform decision making.

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Table 1. NECCTON's key target audiences and the routes to used to engage them.

Target audience	Interests, focus for dissemination and contribution to NECCTON key impacts	Effective dissemination tools and channels
<p>Copernicus Marine Service core service providers: All the MFCs and the TACs for Ocean Colour, Multi-Observations and In situ observations</p>	<p>Copernicus Marine Service MFCs will uptake the integrated NECCTON model system enabling new operational capabilities in simulating: i) HTLs; ii) benthic habitat; iii) Marine pollution and stressors; iv) climate change ocean projections</p> <p>Copernicus Marine Service MFCs will take up the inter-linked modelling framework developed by NECCTON</p> <p>NECCTON results will support the design of the Copernicus hyperspectral CHIME mission</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Website, public summaries, project brochure (relevant to all target groups) • Roadmap to transfer NECCTON to Copernicus Marine Service • NECCTON results presented and discussed in Copernicus Marine Service general meetings (e.g. General Assembly). • Specific meetings will be held with Copernicus Marine Service production centres (MFCs and TACs) as part of Copernicus Marine Service evolution activities. • Ad-hoc meetings with Copernicus Marine Service Science (STAC) and Champion User Advisory Group (CUAG) will be organized. • Data cube visualisation tool
<p>Intermediate users of Copernicus Marine Service National Marine Services, Small-Medium Enterprises in the Copernicus Marine Service database and End-users of Copernicus Marine Service Broad community of users in Copernicus Marine Service database (>55000end-users)</p>	<p>The number of intermediate and end-users of Copernicus Marine Service and worldwide operational centres is expanded supporting further the development of blue economy and ecosystem-based policies.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Website, public summaries, project brochure (relevant to all target groups) • Data cube visualisation tool • Survey of users' needs during and after workshop and training events. • Training – workshops dedicated to Marine Protected Areas for biodiversity conservation and fishery management (Table 3). • Workshops to support co-design of 13 NECCTON case studies • Scientific publications and conferences • 3D immersion visualisation tools for NECCTON products

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Target audience	Interests, focus for dissemination and contribution to NECCTON key impacts	Effective dissemination tools and channels
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media, including Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube. • Press releases targeting wider public
Potential new Copernicus Marine Service users ISSF, IUCN, SPC, IMAR/DRAM, FAO, ICES, CI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The NECCTON products and tools enhance food security by: • Informing the sustainable management of fisheries. Enabled through the provision of validated estimates of maximum sustainable yield of fishes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops and training • Scientific publications and conferences • 3D immersion visualisation tools for NECCTON products •
Up-stream data providers to Copernicus Marine Service ISA, ESA, EUMETSAT, BGC Argo, GOOS, EOOS, EuroGOOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informing stock assessment and the allocation of fisheries quotas, thus contributing to UN SDG 2 (Zero hunger) and UN SDG 12 (sustainable consumption and production patterns) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops and training • Scientific publications and conferences • 3D immersion visualisation tools for NECCTON products •
Policymakers and regional conventions UN-IOC, UN-FAO, UNEP, EU DG MARE, EU DG CNECT OSPAR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine protected areas, implemented in 30% of the global sea by 2030, will be more effective at supporting biodiversity due to NECCTON/ Copernicus Marine Service information on climate change hotspots and bright sites, thus contributing towards UN SDG 13 (Climate action). • Endangered marine species and heavily exploited fishes are better protected or managed by using Copernicus Marine Service/NECCTON capabilities on HTL simulation and climate change ocean • projections, UN SDG 14 (Life below water). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invited to project Workshops and trainings (Table 3) • Scientific publications and conferences • 3D immersion visualisation tools for NECCTON products
Wider scientific and technical community OceanPredict, GEO, GEOSS and GEO Blue Planet UN Decade of Ocean Science	Oceanographers use the NECCTON inter-linked modelling platform as a standard, increasing the effectiveness of science collaborations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications and conferences • 3D immersion visualisation tools for NECCTON products • Five Key project deliverables, including public software and recommendations for

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Target audience	Interests, focus for dissemination and contribution to NECCTON key impacts	Effective dissemination tools and channels
		products uptake and exploitation
General public (civil)	Increased public awareness with respect to the importance of monitoring and preserving marine biodiversity improves public support for such activities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NECCTON project website and social media channels • 3D immersion visualisation tools for NECCTON products
European Commission (policy making)	The EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters" achieve the goal to protect and restore the health of the ocean and waters, by also exploiting the NECCTON models and products as components of the innovated Copernicus Marine service and newly developed European Digital Twin of the Ocean.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copernicus Marine General Assembly • Copernicus National Marine Forum • 3D immersion visualisation tools for NECCTON products
United Nations	Worldwide operational centers adopt the NECCTON integrated modelling approach achieving the "predicted ocean" challenge of the UN Decade for Ocean Science, considered fundamental to adapting and developing strategies and enabling long-term decisions for societal and economic benefits .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copernicus Marine General Assembly • Copernicus National Marine Forum • 3D immersion visualisation tools for NECCTON products

5.2.2.1 Internal dissemination tools

In collaboration with WP1 (Management), WP2 will ensure effective and productive communication across the project through a defined participant network so that communication of results, events, news and opportunities can be shared and targeted as required.

A project email address has been set up neccton@mercator-ocean.fr that is accessible to all partners to support effective communication. Customised email lists have also been created such as the *WP leaders* email list, this will help ensure everyone in the project receives communications that are relevant to them. A NECCTON Microsoft Teams account has been set up with separate channels for different areas of work, for example each WP has its own channel, along with specific channels for activities such as stakeholders, meetings and reporting. This infrastructure is separate from the website with access given only to project participants and other project collaborators. This system offers a place for: confidential file sharing, document drafting; planning and task allocations with reminders as well as facilities to chat about specific topics.

Furthermore, quarterly progress meetings will be held to support open communication across the consortium with all WP leaders present as well as partner representatives as appropriate. Advisory

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Board members will also be invited to join these meetings, many of which will have a science theme (e.g. presentation of modelling results) where research highlights will be presented alongside general project updates.

5.2.2.2 NECCTON brand/graphic identity

Clear, consistent and recognisable branding is essential to effective communication and dissemination. Branding guidelines will include a logo, fonts and colour palettes. The branding will be applied to all project materials including the website, social media, publicity materials and presentations. Templates for communication materials will be produced and made available for all members of the project to use. The branding will clearly identify NECCTON as an EU funded activity. Branding guidelines and logos will be made available through Microsoft Teams for all partners to use in their communications to ensure a consistent approach.

5.2.2.3 Public website

The project website is available at <https://neccton.eu> will be live for at least 5 years after the completion of the project (2028).

An initial NECCTON website went live at the start of the project to ensure visibility from the outset. The website will continue to be developed throughout the life of the project with updates and expansions occurring as required. It will be a repository for open access project information and resources as well as serving as a 'shop-front' for the project.

Current and recently added pages on the website include:

Home: General information about the project, including link to join mailing list.

About: Description of core project objectives and concepts

Impact: Information on what NECCTON will do and how it can be utilised by the community.

Partners: Information about the Consortium, including all partner logos and links to their websites.

News and events: a place to share key project updates and activities

Workshops: A space to share information on project workshops, including registration options. Bespoke registration pages will be created as relevant per workshop. The first registration page was created for the June 2023 Stakeholder Co-design workshop.

Case studies: Details of the case studies in NECCTON, these will be expanded as more information becomes available.

Contacts: details of key project contacts.

The website and all digital and printed communication materials shall be compliant with the relevant Horizon Europe guidelines.

5.2.2.4 Social media

NECCTON will make use of social-media (including Twitter and LinkedIn) to tap-in to existing contact networks, create new groups and encourage followers to keep stakeholders up-to-date with the project. A NECCTON twitter account has been set up [@neccton](#), at the time of writing we have over

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80 followers. The account will continue to keep interested parties informed on project developments and widen our audience engagement. As the project developed it became clear that many of our target audience were active on LinkedIn and a page was set up in June 2023 at <https://www.linkedin.com/company/neccton/> to reach these potential users. As the project continues to develop, and more end users are identified, other social media channels will be considered including Facebook and Instagram if it is found they are more appropriate for specific stakeholder groups.

5.2.2.5 Newsletter

An e-mail newsletter will be sent to all users and interested parties twice a year that will include updates from the project and details of events and products being developed. Later in the project it will highlight use cases. The newsletter will be tailored for an external audience but also sent to project participants to keep them informed of developments throughout NECCTON.

5.2.2.6 Events and publications

NECCTON researchers will attend key events (see *Table 2*) including workshops and working groups with relevant key stakeholders to present and discuss NECCTON developments and results. Oral presentations and discussions will be the typical pathways for communication and dissemination at these meetings. In addition, NECCTON has been and will be discussed during Copernicus Marine meetings such as its General Assembly, and meetings with its advisory bodies: Copernicus Marine Service's Scientific and Technical Advisory Committee (STAC) and Champion Users Advisory Group (CUAG).

Dissemination of NECCTON developments to scientific audiences will primarily be through networking and presentations at scientific conferences and via peer-reviewed articles.

Table 2 Highlights key events that NECCTON plans to attend. This table will be updated as the project develops and more events are confirmed.

Events	Date
Copernicus Marine STAC Meeting	Toulouse, hybrid format, 22 November 2022
Copernicus Marine General Assembly	Brussels, 5-9 June 2023 (repeated annually)
European Digital Ocean Forum 2023	Brussels, 14-15 June 2023
Copernicus Marine Multi-Year Workshop	Toulouse, October 2023 (repeated annually)
Copernicus Marine CUAG Workshop	Online, 18 October 18 2023 (repeated annually)
Copernicus WEKEO CUAG Workshop	Online, 18 October 18 2023 (repeated annually)
EUROGOOS conference	Galway, 3-5 October 2023
8th Annual Meeting of the Ocean Predict Science Team (OPST-8)	Busan, Korea, 6-10 November 2023
MONGOOS General Assembly	14-16 November 2023, Tanger, Morocco
OceanPredict '24	18-22 November 2024, IOC, Paris

5.2.3 General communication factors

Language: the primary language for communications within and external to the project will be English. However, where communications such as press releases relate to a particular geographical area these will be translated as appropriate and distributed to local contacts.

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Gender/cultural issues: All communication activities will consider cultural and gender matters to ensure that products and services appeal to as wide an audience as possible and do not discriminate in any way. All products will be written using non-technical terminology.

Evaluation: Along with the key performance indicators (KPIs) to help evaluate dissemination success as outline in *Table 5*, the effectiveness of NECCTON communication materials will be measured by analysing the audiences reached and engagement with the project. Several tools are available to support this including **Google and Twitter Analytics** to monitor website and social media traffic, and **Altmetric** to monitor online response to scientific papers and analytics from social media feeds.

We will report and evaluate the success of dissemination, exploitation and communication activities through D2.4 "Evaluation of exploitation, dissemination and communication plan" (M48).

5.2.4 NECCTON communication shaped by users

A key aim of NECCTON is to co-design products with users. This will be extended to communication activities where we will seek to ascertain the most appropriate and useful means of communication favoured by each stakeholder. Additional communication channels, including additional social media platforms, will be considered if preferred by users. Stakeholders had their first opportunity to feed into the project and help design its ongoing development through the first co-design stakeholder workshop held on 28-29 June 2023 and then during the final stakeholder workshop in December 2026, they will be asked to contribute to the validation of the new products. In the meantime, MOi will organise regular meetings with the use-cases stakeholders.

5.2.5 Virtual science meetings

To complement the annual in-person meetings, NECCTON will also hold virtual scientific meetings at the mid-way points in the years. This will provide an opportunity for everyone to get together, share their recent scientific advancements and achievements and discuss project developments. All project partners, the advisory board and other interested parties (e.g., representatives of EU projects related to NECCTON: see section 5.2.6) will be invited to join these meetings.

5.2.6 Fostering links with other Horizon Europe projects

NECCTON will continue engaging with other Horizon Europe projects that share or complement our expected impacts, objectives and methods. A strong partnership is in place with the other current Copernicus Service Evolution project (SEAMLESS), which shares with NECCTON several members of the coordination, Steering Committee and advisory board members. Active discussions have been initiated with the project EDITO-Infra and EDIT-Model Lab at the 2nd Digital Ocean forum (Brussels, 14-15 June 2023), both led by Mercator Ocean International, to support the development of the European Digital Twin of the Ocean. New communications links and collaboration plans have been established also with the projects MARCO-BOLO, ACTNOW, FutureMares, EcoScope and Mission Atlantic on the topics of biodiversity conservation, modelling and observation. Co-developments of modelling tools and software are shared between NECCTON and Ocean-ICU, targeting ocean carbon cycle processes, and MarinePlan for the visualization of marine datasets.

The links between NECCTON and the above projects will be strengthened further through the attendance of the annual meetings and workshops, besides direct cross-project communication and coordination of efforts between project leads and researchers.

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5.3 Stakeholders and end-users

Key stakeholders are part of this project as co-designers of the NECCTON products. An extensive list of other stakeholders and possible end-users of NECCTON products was also built based on different databases. MOi has contributed to enlarge this community by engaging contacts belonging to key stakeholder groups, such as the Copernicus National Stakeholder Marine Forum (hereafter ‘Marine Forum’), which aims to co-design services implemented by Mercator Ocean with Member States. The Marine Forum is a consultative assembly to foster interactions between Member States and Mercator Ocean International. In addition, potential users to invite them to the first NECCTON workshop and to send them surveys, were extracted from the Copernicus Marine Service database. The criteria were based on activity, type of data downloaded (biogeochemical model products), and number of datasets downloaded in the last year. We will also engage our champion users from Copernicus Marine and WekEO through the regular workshops we organized with them. Stakeholders can also sign up for project updates by joining the mailing list on the project website (<https://neccton.eu/mailling-list>).

A database containing all these contacts has been set up and is managed according the GDPR rules to ensure transparent, responsible and trustful management of personal data.

The first contact with these stakeholders and end-users will be the NECCTON Stakeholder Workshop, a fully online event held during the 28th-29th of June 2023. During this event, direct discussion took place between users and producers. Moreover, indirect feedback and input were collected using live polls. After the workshop, a survey will be delivered to all these users to collect further details that will help NECCTON contributors to finalize the specifications of the products.

5.3.1 Key stakeholder events

Table 3 shows the key planned stakeholder interaction events over the course of the project

Event	Planned Month
Workshop Stakeholders 1 – Needs and co-design of future products	June 2023
Co-design workshop for use case leaders and stakeholders	February 2024
First demonstration of NECCTON Visualization tool	June 2024
Survey Copernicus Marine Service users, focused on champion users - users of biogeochemical products, of Copernicus marine who agreed to be contacted, stakeholders already contacted through the project, and key contacts of political actors and major account. This survey will help refine training content.	August 2025
Training-workshop 1 – Using NECCTON products (theme 1)	February 2026
Training-workshop 2 – Using NECCTON products (theme 2)	July 2026
Survey NECCTON AB and independent stakeholders and training attendees	August 2026
Final Workshop Stakeholders 2 – Demonstration: Exploration and validation of new products	December 2026

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5.4 Roadmap for uptake of NECCTON by Copernicus Marine Service

The strategic roadmap for the uptake of NECCTON by Copernicus Marine Service:

The mid-to-long-term exploitation strategy of NECCTON consists of a potential integration of new legacy products and services in Copernicus Marine portfolio. The production and delivery of NECCTON's legacy products will follow the evolution strategy of Copernicus Marine Service and its protocols. To prepare the research-to-operations and overall integration of NECCTON's outcomes in Copernicus Marine Service, a **“Strategic roadmap for the uptake of NECCTON by Copernicus Marine Service”** will be prepared during the project, updated following the milestones for the development and evaluation of NECCTON's new and improved modelling capacities as well as improved observation data products, covering all the developments in WP3-WP9 and the exploitation case studies of WP9. A final version of the roadmap will be released in December 2026 at M48 (**D2.3**, led by MOi). As Copernicus Marine Service is policy, user and science driven, the roadmap will cover scientific, technical, user/policy/market aspects, in addition to Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), planning, organization and cost aspects of the research-to-operation transfer.

Research-to-operations: from NECCTON to Copernicus Marine Service

Based on NECCTON results and findings, MOi will define the main NECCTON service elements to be transferred to the operational Copernicus Marine Service, prioritising user and policy needs, technical feasibility, IPR and budget constraints. The potential for research-to-operation transfers will be analysed and monitored during the project's lifetime through interactions between MOi and WP3-8 and through discussion with Copernicus Marine Service production centres (MFCs and TACs). The formal Copernicus Marine Service evolution implementation process managed by MOi will be followed, with a series of reviews that punctuate the development and integration phases of Copernicus Marine Service (e.g., Specification Review for evolutions at Y+2, Design Review for evolutions at Y+1, Acceptance Review before the entry into service at year Y). A specific discussion on NECCTON research-to-operation transfers will be organized by MOi in Copernicus Marine Service Specification and Design reviews. Research-to-operation transfers will be facilitated by the inclusion in NECCTON's consortium of MOi, and all the core developers of the six biogeochemical models operated in Copernicus Marine Service.

Mercator Ocean International, as an entrusted entity for the implementation of Copernicus Marine Service, will ensure the alignment of NECCTON to the overall Copernicus Marine Service evolution needs, strategy and plans and the transferability of NECCTON to Copernicus Marine Service. Other partners are core developers of Copernicus Marine Service MFCs (OGS, UoL, BSH, NERSC) and Copernicus Marine Service TACs (CNR), ensuring the technical alignment between NECCTON and Copernicus Marine Service systems. All the core developer partners, as well as the entrusted entity, engage on a regular basis with data providers (e.g., ESA, EUMETSAT and national space agencies like the Italian Space Agency) to define data needs, channels of data flow, provide feedback on data quality and exploitability.

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Timeline:

The integration of NECCTON products to Copernicus Marine Service is expected to be operated starting from December 2025 (M36), with uptake continuing during the phase 2 of Copernicus 2 (2025-2028) and beyond (post 2028). The “Roadmap for the uptake of NECCTON by Copernicus Marine Service” will be a living document updated following the milestones for the development and evaluation of NECCTON’s new and improved modelling capacities as well as improved observation data products (including summarized outcomes in D9.1). The roadmap will also be informed by stakeholder needs (MS2.2, MS2.4), IPR (Intellectual Property Rights) (D1.1, D1.2), recommendations from the use of NECCTON’s services in use cases (D9.3). A final version of the roadmap will be released at the end of the project as **Key Deliverable D2.3**, covering all the developments in WP3-WP9 and the exploitation case studies of WP9.

Past activities related to the uptake of NECCTON in Copernicus Marine Service:

To inform the Copernicus Marine Service community on potential long-term evolutions of the service driven by NECCTON, the project has already been presented at a number of key meetings, including:

- Copernicus Marine Service General Assembly in Brussels on 5-6 June 2023.
- Scientific and Technical Advisory Committee (STAC) of Copernicus Marine Service in December 2022.

The STAC advises MOi on science and technology issues related to the Copernicus Marine Service delivery and evolution. The STAC particularly assist Mercator Ocean in defining Copernicus Marine Service evolution strategy and to organize some related activities. These activities help to prepare the future versions of the Copernicus Marine Service to better respond to existing and future user demands and needs, fully taking into account the scientific and technological advances relevant for our service. The STAC contributes to the definition and regular updates of our evolution strategy.

5.5 Visualizations

NECCTON partner LOBELIA is currently developing the MyOceanPRO viewer in Copernicus Marine Service that sits on top of the up-to-date live Copernicus Marine Service catalogue of products. The new datasets generated in NECCTON will be formatted and visualized in the same way as the Copernicus Marine Service products by an online dedicated NECCTON viewer based on innovative visualisation software for scientific and broader audiences, fully compliant with Copernicus Marine Service (MyOcean viewer).

The NECCTON data and metadata will be made able in (NetCDF) native format as well as in an analysis-ready-cloud-optimised format that will enable full exploration from the NECCTON viewer in terms of:

- high-resolution graphs and maps,
- high performant data exploration,
- creation of time series by clicking on a point, line or a drawn area on the map,
- zoom-dependant overviews - which display more information as the user zooms in,

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- and data download.

Following the development of the datasets generating by the partners, the preliminary design prototype will be present to the producers and adapted using the first datasets beginning of 2024, in order to prepare the first version of the viewer. The NECCTON viewer will be configured to visualize and distribute NECCTON products supporting user needs. This viewer will guarantee high-availability, visual analysis, flexible data dissemination, and will enable us to monitor (across all dimensions: longitude, latitude, depth, time) which individual product dataset are more frequently downloaded by the investigators and stakeholders.

The products will be available and shared with the users during the trainings scheduled in 2026. Users will be able to visualise and test the products through the viewer prototype datacube.

3D visualizations

EII is in the process of modernizing the OceanViz underwater visualization engine (Steenbeek et al. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.619541>), transferring the code base and updating the visualization toolkit from the deprecated Blender game engine to the modern Unity game development environment. This work is co-funded by EU H2020 project MarinePlan (Grant #101059407).

The modern OceanViz will be made publicly available as an open-source visualization toolkit by December 2026 (M48). With this toolkit, anyone with a bit of programming skill can visualize time-dynamic marine ecosystem data, including model output, in a virtual 3D representation of the underwater world. These 3D representations focus on the impact of communicating change, focussing on facilitating empathic connections with the ecosystem in complement to more conventional scientific data in the form of tables and graphs. Upon delivery, the modern OceanViz will be made available on GitHub for global uptake. The coding upgrade is 50% completed as the MarinePlan project has a tighter time frame.

Project visualizations for broad audiences

Under NECCTON, OceanViz will be used in a few visualizations to convey project aims and key outcomes to the wider public. A NECCTON working group has been established to create project visualizations. This involves defining the scope and story-board of each visualization, and realizing the visualizations through the iterative development of concept art and computer-driven animations. The first visualization produced will explain the rationale and aims of NECCTON aimed at engaging a wider audience base and building interest in the project. It will also help the working group gain experience with the process involved. The working group will also orchestrate the creation of further visualizations that capture key findings of, and across, case studies.

The working group will meet on a per-need basis, and includes the following NECCTON participants:

- Jeroen Steenbeek (EII)
- Mike Pan (EII)
- Corinne Derval (WP2 Lead, MOi)

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- Stefano Ciavatta (Project coordinator, MOi)
- Patrick Lehodey (WP9, Lead, MOi)
- The working group is open to case-studies leaders (from different WP developing new products)

The first visualisation will be ready by December 2023 (M12) and will be shared on the project website, will be uploaded to YouTube and can be used by the NECCTON project community at conferences and meetings. Later in the project the visualisations of the case studies will be broadly shared to across all our communication platforms to engage audiences, share results and promote uptake of products.

6. Copernicus Marine Service dissemination and communication infrastructure

NECCTON will foster an on-going relationship with stakeholders, to support communication measures and develop contact networks to promote the project and its outcomes, with the ultimate goal of maximise project impact through the uptake of NECCTON products. The following core activities will support the implementation of the PEDCR:

- NECCTON has produced and will keep up-to-date a project website and optimise social media throughout the project
- NECCTON will produce a high level non-technical summary of the findings of the project.
- NECCTON will interact with the Advisory Board for ongoing discussion and feedback on the project's direction.
- NECCTON has built links and will continue to interact with all the seven Copernicus Marine Service MFCs' core developers.
- Publication of at least 35 peer-reviewed publications published through GOLD open access, which will be disseminated at conferences and workshops and other events aimed at scientists.
- Dissemination of information about the project and promote project outputs at relevant international conferences, workshops and events throughout the duration of the project.
- NECCTON will ensure that all outward communication will be screened for inclusivity and equality in terms of gender, age, and cultural diversity.

The above activities will be ongoing throughout the project, with a number of publications being submitted beyond the project lifetime.

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Table 4 Communication infrastructure that will be used to reach different NECCTON target audiences; the mark “x” suggests the most common method but is not exclusive.

Target Audience	Website/ Social media	Email	Visualisations	Oral/poster Presentation	Final Comms summary	Project reports	Trainin g events
Copernicus Marine Service MFC (ARC, MED, NWS, GLO, IBI, BS)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Copernicus Marine Service TAC-OC and In situ	x	x	x	x	X		
Copernicus Marine Service Working Groups	x		x	x	x		
Copernicus Marine Service Intermediate and end-users	x	x	x	x			x
Policy-makers UN-IOC, UN-FAO, UNEP, EU DG MARE, EU DG CNECT	x	x	x		x		x
Copernicus Marine Service upstream space and all <i>in situ</i> data providers, including EMODnet	x	x	x	x	x		
Copernicus Climate Change and Land Services	x	x		x			x
Wider scientific and technical community: other H2020 and Horizon Europe projects, OceanPredict, GEO, GEOSS and GEO Blue Planet UN Decade of Ocean Science	x	x	x	x	x		x
European research infrastructures		x					
General Public	x		x				

Figure 2 Timeline for Delivery of key NECCTON communication events and products

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7. Success metrics

The evaluation of the effectiveness of NECCTON communication and dissemination activities will be against a number of KPIs.

Table 5 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) targets for dissemination of scientific and technical results

Activities linked to the project	Expected value by end of NECCTON
All NECCTON datasets from the new products will be viewable in the exploratory viewer	25
Surveys addressed to the AB, stakeholders and users to ensure the usefulness of the NECCTON new products	2
NECCTON products will be proposed to be transferred to Copernicus Marine Service	25
Peer-reviewed scientific publications on NECCTON, led by the project partners	35
Presentations in scientific conferences and key user events (trainings and workshops)	35
Videos linked to the results of the case-studies	8
Stakeholders' workshops and training events reaching in excess of 100 stakeholders per event	2 of each
A new website with relevant content regularly added	5 updates per year
Social media	20 posts per year
Project brochure, and press releases (as appropriate),	1 initially
Newsletters/electronic communications per year.	2 per year

8. Risks to implementation of plan

There are several different elements that need to come together for the effectiveness of dissemination and communication activities, including:

- the timely development and delivery of the project outputs,
- availability of relevant and useful products and interesting outcomes
- efficient management of dissemination activities
- unsuccessful implementation of dissemination and communication activities from all partners
- availability of useful communication materials
- willingness of target audiences to engage and interact with the project.

NECCTON has carefully considered these risks and taken measures to mitigate against them, as outlined below.

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Table 6 Potential risks and contingency measures in relation to the exploitation, dissemination and communication plan

Potential risk	Risk level	Measures to reduce risk
Timely development and delivery of project outputs not fulfilled	Likelihood: low Severity: high Overall risk: Medium	WP leaders have broad experience of coordinating or managing other EC and major national projects. Good project management is foreseen, with close monitoring of partners activities, allowing for early detection of any possible issues. In addition, many partners have successfully worked together in previous research projects and have a history of delivering high quality work. Tasks have been distributed to support a balanced workload across the project.
Availability of relevant and useful products and interesting outcomes	Likelihood: low Severity: high Overall risk: Medium	The project has been designed to provide specific products of direct interest to the key target audience (Copernicus Marine Service), it is therefore likely that outputs from the project will be of interest to target audiences. Products are co-designed with stakeholders to ensure relevance.
Poor management of dissemination activities	Likelihood: low Severity: high Overall risk: Medium	The WP2 lead has previous experience with leading dissemination and communication activities and is the entrusted entity to Copernicus Marine Service and so is well experienced in management and meeting the needs of its core stakeholder.
Unsuccessful implementation of dissemination and communication activities from all partners	Likelihood: low Severity: high Overall risk: Medium	There are several reasons why partners may not implement the planned dissemination activities, major ones being: inexperience, time allocation and external-to-the-project reasons. The WP teams all have previous experience in research output dissemination and so no issues are expected due to inexperience. In addition, all partners have allocated person-months to WP2 to support their activities.
Lack of engagement and interaction from target audiences with the project	Likelihood: low Severity: high Overall risk: Medium	Again the positioning of the lead of WP2 activities (MOi) within the Copernicus Marine Service and broader stakeholder community should help ensure the project is aligned with their needs and of interest to their requirements thus supporting good interactions. Many key users have provided letters of support. Contact will be maintained with stakeholders and end-users throughout the project. The variety of dissemination and communication measures that will be implemented throughout the project should help to ensure project target audiences are reached.